

Striped and Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 6 to 50

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The whole work as pdf file is available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15048>

Abstract

*In this work we shall bring **striped cornered-type** magic squares. These are of two types. One as **striped cornered magic squares**. These are possible only for **even order magic squares**. The second type we call as **striped semi-cornered** magic squares. These are for the **odd order magic squares**. The reason for **semi-cornered** magic squares is that in these case we have one of the corner as magic squares of orders 3 or 5. Combining with one magic rectangle, these becomes are magic rectangles of orders 3×5 or 5×7 . By striped magic squares we understand that magic squares formed only by **equal width magic rectangles**. In these cases the magic rectangles are of type $2 \times n$, where n is the length of the magic rectangle.*

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Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Striped Cornered Magic Rectangles	2
2 Striped Cornered Magic Squares: Even Orders	4
3 Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares: Odd Orders	13
4 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	22

1 Introduction

Let’s understand first about **striped magic rectangles**, i.e., **equal width magic rectangles**. These are of orders 2×4 , 2×4 , 2×4 , etc.

1.1 Striped Cornered Magic Rectangles

We observe from **double digits magic rectangles** that magic rectangles are with width 2, i.e., these are of magic rectangles of type 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 , etc. But this property is not true for the cornered magic rectangles [83]. Below are few examples where we have **cornered magic rectangles** with the property every magic rectangle is with width 2.

Example 1.1. Below is an example of a **striped cornered magic rectangle** of order 6×14 :

52	47	40	37	42	36	41	50	34	46	58	27	12	73	595
33	38	45	48	43	49	44	35	51	39	60	25	74	11	595
26	66	32	64	65	31	22	28	61	30	29	56	4	81	595
59	19	53	21	20	54	63	57	24	55	23	62	78	7	595
71	69	72	5	6	67	70	3	68	2	1	76	77	8	595
14	16	13	80	79	18	15	82	17	83	84	9	10	75	595
255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	

The sums are as follows:

71	69	72	5	6	67	70	3	68	2	1	76	510	12	73	85	58	27	85
14	16	13	80	79	18	15	82	17	83	84	9	510	74	11	85	60	25	85
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85		4	81	85	29	56	85
													78	7	85	23	62	85
26	66	32	64	65	31	22	28	61	30			425	77	8	85	170	170	
59	19	53	21	20	54	63	57	24	55			425	10	75	85			
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85				255	255				
52	47	40	37	42	36	41	50	34	46			425						
33	38	45	48	43	49	44	35	51	39			425						
85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85									

Example 1.2. Below is an example of another **striped cornered magic rectangle** of order 10×12 :

59	61	64	58	68	53	73	48	86	35	18	103	726
62	60	57	63	50	71	76	45	24	97	108	13	726
72	65	54	51	69	52	46	75	22	99	8	113	726
49	56	67	70	55	66	41	80	98	23	104	17	726
74	84	81	39	42	43	44	77	29	92	102	19	726
47	37	40	82	79	78	83	38	34	87	15	106	726
90	26	33	96	94	32	85	28	91	30	115	6	726
31	95	88	25	27	89	36	93	100	21	114	7	726
109	116	2	118	1	4	112	16	107	20	11	110	726
12	5	119	3	120	117	9	105	14	101	10	111	726
605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	605	

The sums are as follows:

109	116	2	118	1	4	112	16	107	20	605	18	103	121	86	35	121	73	48	121	68	53	121
12	5	119	3	120	117	9	105	14	101	605	108	13	121	24	97	121	76	45	121	50	71	121
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121		8	113	121	22	99	121	46	75	121	69	52	121
											104	17	121	98	23	121	41	80	121	55	66	121
90	26	33	96	94	32	85	28	484			102	19	121	29	92	121	44	77	121	242	242	
31	95	88	25	27	89	36	93	484			15	106	121	34	87	121	83	38	121			
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121				115	6	121	91	30	121	363	363				
											114	7	121	100	21	121						
74	84	81	39	42	43	363					11	110	121	484	484							
47	37	40	82	79	78	363					10	111	121									
121	121	121	121	121	121						605	605										
72	65	54	51	242		59	61	64	58	242												
49	56	67	70	242		62	60	57	63	242												
121	121	121	121			121	121	121	121													

Below are links of author's work on **striped** magic squares for even orders from 6 to 20.

1. Striped Magic Squares of Even Orders 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 [88].
2. Striped Magic Squares of 12 [89].
3. 5600+ Striped Magic Squares of Order 16 [90].
4. Striped Magic Squares of 18 [91].
5. 8000+ Striped Magic Squares of 20 [92].

In this work we shall bring **striped cornered** magic squares. These are of two types. One as **striped cornered magic squares**. These are possible only for **even order magic squares**. The second type we call as **striped semi-cornered** magic squares. These are for the **odd order magic squares**. The reason for **semi-cornered** magic squares is that in these case we have one of the corner as magic squares of orders 3 or 5 or magic rectangles of orders 3×5 or 5×7 . By **striped** magic squares we understand that magic squares formed only by **equal width magic rectangles**. In these cases the magic rectangles are of type $2 \times n$, where n is the length of the magic rectangle.

2 Striped Cornered Magic Squares: Even Orders

The section brings **striped** cornered magic squares for even orders from 6 to 50 magic squares. Below are few examples:

6x6	mgc	88	158	62	157	90	111	8x8	semi	312	285	142	278	366	258	110	329	10x10	semi	497	577	537	395	556	615	532	434	538	369	
135	11	28	10	25	3	34	111	253	39	28	34	29	54	11	12	53	260	430	42	43	57	60	61	40	84	17	6	95	505	
56	26	9	27	12	36	1	111	181	30	33	27	40	45	20	13	52	260	366	59	58	44	41	64	37	19	82	83	18	505	
157	6	29	32	7	2	35	111	283	25	38	32	35	7	58	57	8	260	513	35	34	65	68	38	63	87	14	81	20	505	
73	31	8	5	30	33	4	111	244	36	31	37	26	24	41	48	17	260	707	66	67	36	33	39	62	5	96	10	91	505	
134	21	13	20	19	15	23	111	273	44	43	3	55	50	56	4	5	260	409	53	47	52	45	55	51	11	90	98	3	505	
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111	252	21	22	62	10	15	9	61	60	260	589	48	54	49	56	46	50	97	4	25	76	505	
©IJT	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	341	19	18	16	51	6	23	63	64	260	505	80	100	92	13	8	16	73	15	30	78	505	
									46	47	49	14	59	42	2	1	260	415	21	1	9	88	93	85	28	86	71	23	505	
									260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	253	533	75	27	29	77	12	31	7	69	99	79	505	
																			26	74	72	24	89	70	94	32	2	22	505	
																			505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	583

12x12	mgc	927	867	910	745	942	658	1112	968	723	878	840	870	14x14	mgc	1282	1522	1455	1695	744	1538	1824	1085	1400	1494	1430	1317	1141	1379
941	62	84	63	81	60	85	52	93	40	105	17	128	870	1361	113	116	82	83	79	118	128	69	149	48	170	27	19	178	1379
765	83	61	82	64	86	59	94	51	106	39	126	19	870	1182	84	81	115	114	74	123	71	126	148	49	172	25	189	8	1379
853	53	91	90	56	87	58	95	50	111	34	127	18	870	1536	117	124	75	78	120	77	133	64	144	53	40	157	12	185	1379
1014	92	54	55	89	57	88	49	96	33	112	20	125	870	1254	80	73	122	119	121	76	130	67	56	141	29	168	4	193	1379
693	43	41	103	101	100	98	46	48	36	109	16	129	870	1313	62	65	127	134	131	72	68	129	46	151	33	164	181	16	1379
1016	102	104	42	44	45	47	99	97	110	35	130	15	870	1483	135	132	70	63	66	125	61	136	137	60	163	34	187	10	1379
649	77	67	76	65	74	70	72	79	107	38	131	14	870	1380	139	45	147	142	54	59	150	52	51	146	153	44	13	184	1379
933	68	78	69	80	71	75	73	66	37	108	13	132	870	1370	58	152	50	55	143	138	47	145	57	140	155	42	175	22	1379
1000	4	1	135	8	142	139	143	5	9	12	138	134	870	1452	28	35	161	166	41	26	160	158	43	167	32	165	176	21	1379
856	141	144	10	137	3	6	2	140	136	133	7	11	870	1432	169	162	36	31	156	171	37	39	154	30	38	159	20	177	1379
850	24	122	25	29	119	32	115	28	21	123	114	118	870	1517	183	192	186	23	1	6	24	182	3	7	180	195	18	179	1379
	121	23	120	116	26	113	30	117	124	22	31	27	870	1176	14	5	11	174	196	191	173	15	194	190	17	2	188	9	1379
©IJT	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	1471	85	111	100	109	89	107	106	92	104	94	95	101	87	99	1379
															112	86	97	88	108	90	91	105	93	103	102	96	110	98	1379
														©IJT	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

16x16	mgc	2018	2306	2041	1836	1914	2351	1558	2931	1835	2040	1903	2020	1677	2614	1796	2056
2344	125	131	130	128	117	140	113	144	89	168	81	176	47	210	33	224	2056
1894	132	126	127	129	139	118	143	114	167	90	175	82	209	48	43	214	2056
2510	121	135	134	124	138	119	142	115	91	166	83	174	45	212	35	222	2056
1395	136	122	123	133	120	137	116	141	165	92	173	84	211	46	221	36	2056
2489	105	151	107	149	148	110	146	112	164	93	172	85	208	49	220	37	2056
1594	152	106	150	108	109	147	111	145	94	163	86	171	207	50	219	38	2056
2306	97	159	99	157	156	154	102	104	162	95	170	87	51	206	39	218	2056
2088	160	98	158	100	101	103	155	153	96	161	88	169	52	205	40	217	2056
2260	69	187	71	185	184	183	75	76	77	179	79	177	53	204	41	216	2056
1749	188	70	186	72	73	74	182	181	180	78	178	80	203	54	215	42	2056
2271	57	199	59	197	196	195	63	64	65	191	67	189	55	202	223	34	2056
1598	200	58	198	60	61	62	194	193	192	66	190	68	201	56	213	44	2056
2223	17	239	19	237	236	22	234	24	25	231	27	228	229	30	226	32	2056
2368	240	18	238	20	21	235	23	233	232	26	230	29	28	227	31	225	2056
1751	253	11	3	255	252	6	250	8	9	247	242	245	244	14	1	16	2056
	4	246	254	2	5	251	7	249	248	10	15	12	13	243	256	241	2056
©IJT	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

18x18	mgc	2476	3048	2899	2761	3092	2748	3301	3028	3092	2875	2616	3157	2563	2638	3011	3316	3104	2925
2743	177	180	146	147	143	182	192	133	213	112	234	91	83	242	52	273	302	23	2925
2878	148	145	179	178	138	187	135	190	212	113	236	89	245	80	303	22	265	60	2925
3349	181	188	139	142	184	141	197	128	208	117	104	221	76	249	58	267	36	289	2925
2237	144	137	186	183	185	140	194	131	120	205	93	232	68	257	13	312	27	298	2925
3644	126	129	191	198	195	136	132	193	110	215	97	228	253	72	284	41	32	293	2925
3119	199	196	134	127	130	189	125	200	201	124	227	98	251	74	278	47	25	300	2925
2262	203	109	211	206	118	123	214	116	115	210	217	108	77	248	15	310	61	264	2925
2690	122	216	114	119	207	202	111	209	121	204	219	106	239	86	304	21	261	64	2925
3361	92	99	225	230	105	90	224	222	107	231	96	229	240	85	40	285	283	42	2925
2957	233	226	100	95	220	235	101	103	218	94	102	223	84	241	19	306	288	37	2925
2639	247	256	250	87	65	70	88	246	67	71	244	259	82	243	319	6	321	4	2925
3312	78	69	75	238	260	255	237	79	258	254	81	66	252	73	274	51	287	38	2925
2704	149	175	164	173	153	171	170	156	168	158	159	165	151	163	299	26	31	294	2925
3006	176	150	161	152	172	154	155	169	157	167	166	160	174	162	17	308	56	269	2925
2951	324	322	271	12	314	279	62	5	301	63	7	39	16	311	272	270	49	8	2925
3030	1	3	54	313	11	46	263	320	24	262	318	286	309	14	53	55	276	317	2925
2843	266	307	45	57	275	29	315	20	35	277	291	323	9	292	282	44	28	30	2925
	59	18	280	268	50	296	10	305	290	48	34	2	316	33	43	281	297	295	2925
©IJT	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

20x20	mgc	3514	4501	4003	4233	4140	3859	3807	4262	3858	3659	4511	3799	3617	4983	3546	4286	3445	4884	3283	4010	
3774	197	203	202	200	189	212	185	216	161	240	153	248	117	284	105	296	57	344	359	42	4010	
4346	204	198	199	201	211	190	215	186	239	162	247	154	283	118	295	106	343	58	56	345	4010	
4397	193	207	206	196	210	191	214	187	163	238	155	246	119	282	107	294	59	342	43	358	4010	
2833	208	194	195	205	192	209	188	213	237	164	245	156	281	120	293	108	341	60	357	44	4010	
4489	177	223	179	221	220	182	218	184	236	165	244	157	280	121	292	109	340	61	356	45	4010	
4041	224	178	222	180	181	219	183	217	166	235	158	243	279	122	291	110	62	339	46	355	4010	
3845	174	231	171	229	228	226	169	176	234	167	242	159	123	278	111	290	338	63	354	47	4010	
4448	227	170	230	172	173	175	232	225	168	233	160	241	125	276	112	289	64	337	48	353	4010	
3949	141	259	143	257	256	255	147	148	149	251	151	249	124	277	113	288	65	336	49	352	4010	
3949	260	142	258	144	145	146	254	253	252	150	250	152	275	126	287	114	335	66	351	50	4010	
4536	129	271	131	269	268	267	135	136	261	263	139	137	127	274	115	286	67	334	51	350	4010	
2847	272	130	270	132	133	134	266	265	140	138	262	264	273	128	285	116	333	68	349	52	4010	
4877	89	311	91	309	308	94	306	96	97	303	99	301	300	102	298	104	332	69	348	53	4010	
3215	312	90	310	92	93	307	95	305	304	98	302	100	101	299	103	297	70	331	54	347	4010	
4279	73	327	75	325	324	78	322	80	81	319	83	317	316	86	314	88	330	71	346	55	4010	
4076	328	74	326	76	77	323	79	321	320	82	318	84	85	315	87	313	72	329	41	360	4010	
4357	22	363	32	27	28	368	380	35	361	367	37	25	375	36	39	371	24	378	372	370	4010	
3959	379	38	369	374	373	33	21	366	40	34	364	376	26	365	362	30	377	23	29	31	4010	
3973	2	383	12	7	8	388	400	15	381	390	17	5	395	16	19	391	398	4	387	392	4010	
	399	18	389	394	393	13	1	386	20	11	384	396	6	385	382	10	3	397	14	9	4010	
©IJT	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

22x22	mgc	5536	4751	6272	4747	6201	5334	4661	5881	4940	5382	5210	5700	4426	5315	5106	6884	4781	5327	5128	5014	5439	5335
5120	257	260	226	227	223	262	272	213	293	192	314	171	163	322	132	353	382	103	67	418	426	59	5335
5621	228	225	259	258	218	267	215	270	292	193	316	169	325	160	383	102	345	140	431	54	65	420	5335
6020	261	268	219	222	264	221	277	208	288	197	184	301	156	329	138	347	116	369	3	482	31	454	5335
3699	224	217	266	263	265	220	274	211	200	285	173	312	148	337	93	392	107	378	446	39	51	434	5335
6030	206	209	271	278	275	216	212	273	190	295	177	308	333	152	364	121	112	373	10	475	23	462	5335
5239	279	276	214	207	210	269	205	280	281	204	307	178	331	154	358	127	105	380	4	481	20	465	5335
6478	283	189	291	286	198	203	294	196	195	290	297	188	157	328	95	390	141	344	412	73	57	428	5335
4654	202	296	194	199	287	282	191	289	201	284	299	186	319	166	384	101	341	144	7	478	41	444	5335
5523	172	179	305	310	185	170	304	302	187	311	176	309	320	165	120	365	363	122	439	46	456	29	5335
5525	313	306	180	175	300	315	181	183	298	174	182	303	164	321	99	386	368	117	425	60	432	53	5335
3606	327	336	330	167	145	150	168	326	147	151	324	339	162	323	399	86	401	84	406	79	469	16	5335
6028	158	149	155	318	340	335	317	159	338	334	161	146	332	153	354	131	367	118	417	68	457	28	5335
6226	229	255	244	253	233	251	250	236	248	238	239	245	231	243	379	106	111	374	419	66	38	447	5335
4583	256	230	241	232	252	234	235	249	237	247	246	240	254	242	97	388	136	349	422	63	476	9	5335
5831	404	402	350	92	394	359	142	85	381	143	87	119	96	391	352	351	129	88	409	76	437	48	5335
5192	81	83	135	393	91	126	343	400	104	342	398	366	389	94	133	134	356	397	2	483	436	49	5335
4726	346	387	125	137	355	115	395	100	109	357	371	403	89	372	362	124	108	110	33	452	35	450	5335
6342	139	98	360	348	130	370	90	385	376	128	114	82	396	113	123	361	377	375	13	472	415	70	5335
4541	449	5	410	468	448	470	424	34	435	461	78	466	45	26	44	430	71	64	56	416	21	14	5335
5482	36	480	75	17	37	15	61	451	50	24	407	19	440	459	441	55	414	421	429	69	464	471	5335
5569	1	27	453	8	455	405	442	433	11	18	12	427	423	443	6	22	25	445	413	411	408	47	5335
	484	458	32	477	30	80	43	52	474	467	473	58	62	42	479	463	460	40	72	74	77	438	5335
	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

24x24	mgc	6806	7122	7220	6571	7487	5436	8570	5000	8252	7058	7435	6388	7148	5989	7122	7089	6342	8362	6603	6932	5611	7441	7268	6924	
7167	285	291	290	288	277	300	273	304	249	328	241	336	205	372	193	384	152	425	447	130	506	71	526	51	6924	
6457	292	286	287	289	299	278	303	274	327	250	335	242	371	206	383	194	431	146	144	433	69	508	509	68	6924	
7396	281	295	294	284	298	279	302	275	251	326	243	334	207	370	195	382	147	430	131	446	86	491	60	517	6924	
6742	296	282	283	293	280	297	276	301	325	252	333	244	369	208	381	196	429	148	445	132	489	88	58	519	6924	
5876	265	311	267	309	308	270	306	272	324	253	332	245	368	209	380	197	428	149	444	133	78	499	516	61	6924	
8087	312	266	310	268	269	307	271	305	254	323	246	331	367	210	379	198	150	427	134	443	502	75	522	55	6924	
7239	262	319	259	317	316	314	257	264	322	255	330	247	211	366	199	378	426	151	442	135	496	81	66	511	6924	
6238	315	258	318	260	261	263	320	313	256	321	248	329	213	364	200	377	145	432	136	441	490	87	510	67	6924	
6783	229	347	231	345	344	343	235	236	237	339	239	337	212	365	201	376	153	424	137	440	495	82	515	62	6924	
7478	348	230	346	232	233	234	342	341	340	238	338	240	363	214	375	202	423	154	439	138	80	497	49	528	6924	
5764	217	359	219	357	356	355	223	224	349	351	227	225	215	362	203	374	155	422	139	438	500	77	520	57	6924	
8108	360	218	358	220	221	222	354	353	228	226	350	352	361	216	373	204	421	156	437	140	83	494	63	514	6924	
5845	177	399	179	397	396	182	394	184	185	391	187	389	388	190	386	192	420	157	436	141	498	79	518	59	6924	
7462	400	178	398	180	181	395	183	393	392	186	390	188	189	387	191	385	158	419	142	435	505	72	525	52	6924	
6984	161	415	163	413	412	166	410	168	169	407	171	405	404	174	402	176	418	159	434	143	84	493	64	513	6924	
6391	416	162	414	164	165	411	167	409	408	170	406	172	173	403	175	401	160	417	129	448	76	501	56	521	6924	
7386	110	451	120	115	116	456	468	123	449	455	125	113	463	124	127	459	112	466	460	458	504	73	524	53	6924	
6877	467	126	457	462	461	121	109	454	128	122	452	464	114	453	450	118	465	111	117	119	85	492	65	512	6924	
7540	90	471	100	95	96	476	488	103	469	478	105	93	483	104	107	479	486	92	475	480	70	507	50	527	6924	
7277	487	106	477	482	481	101	89	474	108	99	472	484	94	473	470	98	91	485	102	97	74	503	54	523	6924	
6425	44	530	46	27	28	29	537	45	538	43	42	30	551	536	552	35	543	32	37	544	529	546	541	539	6924	
7823	533	47	531	550	549	548	40	532	39	534	535	547	26	41	25	542	34	545	540	33	48	31	36	38	6924	
5907	575	4	576	554	19	5	561	22	562	21	18	6	570	560	565	11	567	8	13	568	553	563	20	3	6924	
	2	573	1	23	558	572	16	555	15	556	559	571	7	17	12	566	10	569	564	9	24	14	557	574	6924	
	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924

26x26	mgc	9671	9439	7203	9652	7588	10628	7094	9627	9443	7504	8672	9866	7011	9270	9537	8811	9509	8325	9284	7653	8426	10054	7457	9346	8955	8801	
9094	353	356	322	323	319	358	368	309	389	288	410	267	259	418	228	449	478	199	163	514	522	155	50	627	52	625	8801	
7534	324	321	355	354	314	363	311	366	388	289	412	265	421	256	479	198	441	236	527	150	161	516	634	43	642	35	8801	
10152	357	364	315	318	360	317	373	304	384	293	280	397	252	425	234	443	212	465	99	578	127	550	67	610	70	607	8801	
6962	320	313	362	359	361	316	370	307	296	381	269	408	244	433	189	488	203	474	542	135	147	530	672	5	667	10	8801	
10838	302	305	367	374	371	312	308	369	286	391	273	404	429	248	460	217	208	469	106	571	119	558	600	77	2	675	8801	
7620	375	372	310	303	306	365	301	376	377	300	403	274	427	250	454	223	201	476	100	577	116	561	26	651	598	79	8801	
9424	379	285	387	382	294	299	390	292	291	386	393	284	253	424	191	486	237	440	508	169	153	524	617	60	613	64	8801	
9143	298	392	290	295	383	378	287	385	297	380	395	282	415	262	480	197	437	240	103	574	137	540	90	587	604	73	8801	
9217	268	275	401	406	281	266	400	398	283	407	272	405	416	261	216	461	459	218	535	142	552	125	33	644	69	608	8801	
8766	409	402	276	271	396	411	277	279	394	270	278	399	260	417	195	482	464	213	521	156	528	149	641	36	91	586	8801	
7344	423	432	426	263	241	246	264	422	243	247	420	435	258	419	495	182	497	180	502	175	565	112	76	601	662	15	8801	
10016	254	245	251	414	436	431	413	255	434	430	257	242	428	249	450	227	463	214	513	164	553	124	603	74	645	32	8801	
9207	325	351	340	349	329	347	346	332	344	334	335	341	327	339	475	202	207	470	515	162	134	543	655	22	56	621	8801	
8701	352	326	337	328	348	330	331	345	333	343	342	336	350	338	193	484	232	445	518	159	572	105	84	593	20	657	8801	
8654	500	498	446	188	490	455	238	181	477	239	184	215	192	487	448	447	225	183	505	172	533	144	27	650	88	589	8801	
8003	177	179	231	489	187	222	439	496	200	438	493	462	485	190	229	230	452	494	98	579	532	145	637	40	58	619	8801	
9086	442	483	221	233	451	211	491	196	205	453	467	499	185	468	458	220	204	206	129	548	131	546	61	616	614	63	8801	
7130	235	194	456	444	226	466	186	481	472	224	210	178	492	209	219	457	473	471	109	568	511	166	9	668	623	54	8801	
9189	545	101	506	564	544	566	520	130	531	557	174	562	141	122	140	526	167	160	152	512	117	110	65	612	597	80	8801	
9844	132	576	171	113	133	111	157	547	146	120	503	115	536	555	537	151	510	517	525	165	560	567	594	83	12	665	8801	
9303	97	123	549	104	551	501	538	529	107	114	108	523	519	539	102	118	121	541	509	507	504	143	595	82	643	34	8801	
8421	580	554	128	573	126	176	139	148	570	563	569	154	158	138	575	559	556	136	168	170	173	534	611	66	21	656	8801	
8407	24	636	37	46	38	673	39	659	89	632	635	48	618	620	602	591	85	647	44	81	19	25	590	654	6	663	8801	
8909	653	41	640	631	639	4	638	18	588	45	42	629	59	57	75	86	592	30	633	596	658	652	87	23	671	14	8801	
9061	660	53	605	584	582	47	49	626	96	664	666	28	585	1	62	68	622	29	583	669	661	31	78	674	71	7	8801	
	17	624	72	93	95	630	628	51	581	13	11	649	92	676	615	609	55	648	94	8	16	646	599	3	606	670	8801	
	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801	8801

28x28	mgc	11812	10139	11923	9652	13296	9597	11014	10126	10906	11000	12156	8832	12070	12068	9970	12951	8074	12555	9961	12477	10758	11472	9382	11805	11084	11154	10496	10990	
11197	389	395	394	392	381	404	377	408	353	432	345	440	309	476	297	488	256	529	551	234	610	175	630	155	46	739	90	695	10990	
9153	396	390	391	393	403	382	407	378	431	354	439	346	475	310	487	298	535	250	248	537	173	612	613	172	53	732	694	91	10990	
12934	385	399	398	388	402	383	406	379	355	430	347	438	311	474	299	486	251	534	235	550	190	595	164	621	70	715	772	13	10990	
9714	400	386	387	397	384	401	380	405	429	356	437	348	473	312	485	300	533	252	549	236	593	192	162	623	6	779	742	43	10990	
10313	369	415	371	413	412	374	410	376	428	357	436	349	472	313	484	301	532	253	548	237	182	603	620	165	85	700	717	68	10990	
11653	416	370	414	372	373	411	375	409	358	427	350	435	471	314	483	302	254	531	238	547	606	179	629	156	731	54	725	60	10990	
10385	366	423	363	421	420	418	361	368	426	359	434	351	315	470	303	482	530	255	546	239	600	185	170	615	59	726	778	7	10990	
12232	419	362	422	364	365	367	424	417	360	425	352	433	317	468	304	481	249	536	240	545	594	191	614	171	712	73	784	1	10990	
11266	333	451	335	449	448	447	339	340	341	443	343	441	316	469	305	480	257	528	241	544	599	186	619	166	768	17	55	730	10990	
10423	452	334	450	336	337	338	446	445	444	342	442	344	467	318	479	306	527	258	543	242	184	601	153	632	748	37	67	718	10990	
11307	321	463	323	461	460	459	327	328	453	455	331	329	319	466	307	478	259	526	243	542	604	181	624	161	771	14	79	706	10990	
8988	464	322	462	324	325	326	458	457	332	330	454	456	465	320	477	308	525	260	541	244	187	598	167	618	65	720	762	23	10990	
11249	281	503	283	501	500	286	498	288	289	495	291	493	492	294	490	296	524	261	540	245	602	183	622	163	71	714	52	733	10990	
13112	504	282	502	284	285	499	287	497	496	290	494	292	293	491	295	489	262	523	246	539	609	176	626	159	63	722	31	754	10990	
9842	265	519	267	517	516	270	514	272	273	511	275	509	508	278	506	280	522	263	538	247	188	597	168	617	696	89	39	746	10990	
12380	520	266	518	268	269	515	271	513	512	274	510	276	277	507	279	505	264	521	233	552	180	605	160	625	38	747	11	774	10990	
9339	214	555	224	219	220	560	572	227	553	559	229	217	567	228	231	563	216	570	564	562	608	177	628	157	41	744	35	750	10990	
11455	571	230	561	566	565	225	213	558	232	226	556	568	218	557	554	222	569	215	221	223	189	596	169	616	729	56	10	775	10990	
12199	194	575	204	199	200	580	592	207	573	582	209	197	587	208	211	583	196	579	584	174	611	154	631	782	3	34	751	10990		
9773	591	210	581	586	585	205	193	578	212	203	576	588	198	577	574	202	195	589	206	201	178	607	158	627	699	86	724	61	10990	
11656	148	634	150	131	132	133	641	149	642	147	146	134	655	640	656	139	647	136	141	648	633	650	645	643	728	57	42	743	10990	
9904	637	151	635	654	653	652	144	636	143	638	639	651	130	145	129	646	138	649	644	137	152	135	140	142	64	721	781	4	10990	
11447	679	108	680	658	123	109	665	126	666	125	122	110	674	664	669	115	671	112	117	672	657	667	124	107	688	97	710	75	10990	
11798	106	677	105	127	662	676	120	659	119	660	663	675	111	121	116	670	114	673	668	113	128	118	661	678	707	78	686	99	10990	
10536	723	687	87	681	760	100	713	29	755	74	96	51	84	83	757	33	745	76	77	705	44	749	26	704	683	682	21	765	10990	
11327	62	98	698	104	25	685	72	756	30	711	689	734	701	702	28	752	40	709	708	80	741	36	759	81	102	103	764	20	10990	
11148	780	8	2	735	32	740	766	66	82	773	94	727	737	101	738	697	9	770	27	16	18	69	763	736	24	95	692	693	10990	
	5	777	783	50	753	45	19	719	703	12	691	58	48	684	47	88	776	15	758	769	767	716	22	49	761	690	93	92	10990	
	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990

30x30	mgc	14022	12246	13024	14436	14769	10013	14880	13642	13009	14750	13618	14653	11597	14553	14467	11893	13358	15365	11565	12664	13649	13638	13478	14076	13738	13594	13175	16530	11533	13515	
13028	465	468	434	435	431	470	480	421	501	400	522	379	371	530	340	561	590	311	275	626	634	267	162	739	164	737	41	860	878	23	13515	
12826	436	433	467	466	426	475	423	478	500	401	524	377	533	368	591	310	553	348	639	262	273	628	746	155	754	147	819	82	24	877	13515	
14421	469	476	427	430	472	429	485	416	496	405	392	509	364	537	346	555	324	577	211	690	239	662	179	722	182	719	884	17	886	15	13515	
12850	432	425	474	471	473	428	482	419	408	493	381	520	356	545	301	600	315	586	654	247	259	642	784	117	779	122	75	826	107	794	13515	
13981	414	417	479	486	483	424	420	481	398	503	385	516	541	360	572	329	320	581	218	683	231	670	712	189	114	787	844	57	811	90	13515	
13465	487	484	422	415	418	477	413	488	489	412	515	386	539	362	566	335	313	588	212	689	228	673	138	763	710	191	61	840	795	106	13515	
14653	491	397	499	494	406	411	502	404	403	498	505	396	365	536	303	598	349	552	620	281	265	636	729	172	725	176	58	843	47	854	13515	
13221	410	504	402	407	495	490	399	497	409	492	507	394	527	374	592	309	549	352	215	686	249	652	202	699	716	185	98	803	80	821	13515	
14738	380	387	513	518	393	378	512	510	395	519	384	517	528	373	328	573	571	330	647	254	664	237	145	756	181	720	822	79	805	96	13515	
11017	521	514	388	383	508	523	389	391	506	382	390	511	372	529	307	594	576	325	633	268	640	261	753	148	203	698	74	827	791	110	13515	
12038	535	544	538	375	353	358	376	534	355	359	532	547	370	531	607	294	609	292	614	287	677	224	188	713	774	127	62	839	851	50	13515	
16678	366	357	363	526	548	543	525	367	546	542	369	354	540	361	562	339	575	326	625	276	665	236	715	186	757	144	25	876	20	881	13515	
14232	437	463	452	461	441	459	458	444	456	446	447	453	439	451	587	314	319	582	627	274	246	655	767	134	168	733	83	818	833	68	13515	
13687	464	438	449	440	460	442	443	457	445	455	454	448	462	450	305	596	344	557	630	271	684	217	196	705	132	769	887	14	823	78	13515	
14310	612	610	558	300	602	567	350	293	589	351	296	327	304	599	560	559	337	295	617	284	645	256	139	762	200	701	814	87	105	796	13515	
9071	289	291	343	601	299	334	551	608	312	550	605	574	597	302	341	342	564	606	210	691	644	257	749	152	170	731	816	85	853	48	13515	
15239	554	595	333	345	563	323	603	308	317	565	579	611	297	580	570	332	316	318	241	660	243	658	173	728	726	175	63	838	868	33	13515	
12960	347	306	568	556	338	578	298	593	584	336	322	290	604	321	331	569	585	583	221	680	623	278	121	780	735	166	30	871	866	35	13515	
12067	657	213	618	676	656	678	632	242	643	669	286	674	253	234	252	638	279	272	264	624	229	222	177	724	709	192	857	44	850	51	13515	
16124	244	688	283	225	245	223	269	659	258	232	615	227	648	667	649	263	622	629	637	277	672	679	706	195	124	777	60	841	22	879	13515	
12870	209	235	661	216	663	613	650	641	219	226	220	635	631	651	214	230	233	653	621	619	616	255	707	194	755	146	16	885	100	801	13515	
13945	692	666	240	685	238	288	251	260	682	675	681	266	270	250	687	671	668	248	280	282	285	646	723	178	133	768	845	56	93	808	13515	
14329	136	748	149	158	150	785	151	771	201	744	747	160	730	732	714	703	197	759	156	193	131	137	702	766	118	775	855	46	72	829	13515	
12985	765	153	752	743	751	116	750	130	700	157	154	741	171	169	187	198	704	142	745	708	770	764	199	135	783	126	865	36	91	810	13515	
12985	772	165	717	696	694	159	161	738	208	776	778	140	697	113	174	180	734	141	695	781	773	143	190	786	183	119	812	89	40	861	13515	
13736	129	736	184	205	207	742	740	163	693	125	123	761	204	788	727	721	167	760	206	120	128	758	711	115	718	782	847	54	2	899	13515	
12958	97	894	10	890	858	101	37	5	789	45	59	18	820	862	103	817	6	807	797	846	898	799	852	65	27	53	893	88	870	109	13515	
13802	804	7	891	11	43	800	864	896	112	856	842	883	81	39	798	84	895	94	104	55	3	102	49	836	874	848	8	813	31	792	13515	
13719	892	832	849	70	863	815	875	67	790	13	21	825	4	889	828	835	92	19	108	802	71	28	34	77	64	859	29	869	95	900	13515	
	9	69	52	831	38	86	26	834	111	888	880	76	897	12	73	66	809	882	793	99	830	873	867	824	837	42	872	32	806	1	13515	
	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515

3 Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares: Odd Orders

The section brings **semi-striped** cornered magic squares for even orders from 7 to 49 magic squares. As we explained above, by **semi-striped** we understand that in these cases we have one of the corner as magic squares of orders 3 or 5 or **magic rectangles** of orders 3×5 or 5×7 . Below are few examples:

7x7	semi	154 198 165 197 145 192 174	9x9	semi	437 226 448 311 291 477 291 291 549	11x11	mgc	761 755 584 685 641 686 638 759 794 407 671		
163	26 27 22	37 13 20 30	175	401	49 31 52 37 36	58 24 4 78	369	677	60 59 64 50 72 46 76 14 108 11 111	671
174	21 25 29	4 46 44 6	175	267	48 40 32 39 46	6 76 54 28	369	684	65 61 57 81 41 84 38 110 12 86 36	671
158	28 23 24	34 16 11 39	175	367	30 42 45 53 35	3 79 77 5	369	525	58 63 62 52 70 53 69 112 10 87 35	671
195	19 47 2 17 41 42 7	175	459	34 41 47 33 50	72 10 7 75	369	750	37 56 83 77 44 79 51	26 96 4 118	671
208	31 3 48 33 9 8 43	175	415	44 51 29 43 38	66 16 63 19	369	485	85 66 39 45 78 43 71	27 95 105 17	671
152	49 18 5 15 40 36 12	175	269	61 18 14 13 55 71 56 73 8	369	935	40 68 75 80 49 67 48	119 3 100 22	671	
	1 32 45 35 10 14 38	175	378	21 64 68 69 27 11 26 9 74	369	780	82 54 47 42 73 55 74	19 103 34 88	671	
©IJT	175 175 175 175 175 175 175	175	424	15 80 81 20 59 25 12 17 60	369	334	109 114 25 6 24 91 104 29 107 32 30	671		
				67 2 1 62 23 57 70 65 22	369	831	13 8 97 116 98 31 18 93 15 90 92	671		
			©IJT	369 369 369 369 369 369 369 369 369	341	709	21 23 113 106 5 94 1 102 2 115 89	671		
							101 99 9 16 117 28 121 20 120 7 33	671		
						©IJT	671 671 671 671 671 671 671 671 671 671 671	671		

13x13	mgc	1213 931 1150 1126 968 1081 1124 1203 1106 1381 755 1222 1105	15x15	mgc	2011 1207 2109 1234 1730 1666 1937 1540 1845 1743 1508 1832 1817 1551 1695	
1181	84 75 93 91 82	102 68 61 109 150 20 8 162	1105	1414	112 111 116 102 124 98 128 66 160 63 163 22 204 196 30	1695
1357	74 97 81 90 83	65 105 72 98 42 128 44 126	1105	2123	117 113 109 133 93 136 90 162 64 138 88 213 13 26 200	1695
657	92 94 85 76 78	99 71 121 49 161 9 141 29	1105	1212	110 115 114 104 122 105 121 164 62 139 87 32 194 212 14	1695
1121	87 80 89 73 96	45 125 58 112 157 13 144 26	1105	1803	89 108 135 129 96 131 103 78 148 56 170 182 44 216 10	1695
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961	122 70 52 124 120 64 101 53 59	22 148 165 5 1105	1701	92 119 127 132 101 120 100	171 55 152 74 15 211 27 199	1695
1303	48 100 118 46 50 106 69 117 111	30 140 33 137 1105	1729	134 107 99 94 125 106 126	71 155 86 140 174 52 46 180	1695
1365	116 110 67 51 47 108 107 55 104	19 151 36 134 1105	1534	161 166 77 58 76 143 156 81 159 84 82	12 214 28 198	1695
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1121	168 43 166 169 131 16 25 23 28 155 7 133 41	1105	1598	176 190 42 23 219 19 189 187 5 4 34 11 177 202 217	1695	
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©IJT	1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105 1105	1105	1541	208 193 206 29 209 1 3 195 201 38 8 205 2 181 16	1695	
				18 33 20 197 17 225 223 31 25 188 218 21 224 45 210	1695	
			©IJT	1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695 1695	1695	

17x17	mgc	2282	2152	2633	2773	1749	2802	2713	2513	2203	2635	2205	2427	2755	2404	2309	2885	2465
2596	144	135	153	151	142	162	128	121	169	210	80	68	222	27	263	262	28	2465
2516	134	157	141	150	143	125	165	132	158	102	188	104	186	55	235	255	35	2465
2530	152	154	145	136	138	159	131	181	109	221	69	201	89	281	9	248	42	2465
2115	147	140	149	133	156	105	185	118	172	217	73	204	86	50	240	32	258	2465
2290	148	139	137	155	146	174	116	173	117	98	192	94	196	29	261	246	44	2465
2833	182	130	112	184	180	124	161	113	119	82	208	225	65	288	2	268	22	2465
2616	108	160	178	106	110	166	129	177	171	90	200	93	197	245	45	11	279	2465
2703	176	170	127	111	107	168	167	115	164	79	211	96	194	269	21	14	276	2465
1999	114	120	163	179	183	122	123	175	126	206	84	220	70	49	241	277	13	2465
2180	213	227	87	195	198	81	190	212	71	66	72	74	199	48	242	243	47	2465
3005	77	63	203	95	92	209	100	78	219	224	218	216	91	60	230	1	289	2465
2422	228	103	226	229	191	76	85	83	88	215	67	193	101	253	37	8	282	2465
2751	62	187	64	61	99	214	205	207	202	75	223	97	189	231	59	20	270	2465
2137	272	3	31	260	249	244	40	232	39	12	237	252	238	257	19	24	56	2465
2133	18	287	259	30	41	46	250	58	251	278	53	38	52	33	271	266	234	2465
2614	285	286	280	15	54	57	34	283	239	25	17	43	267	26	284	16	254	2465
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19x19	mgc	2935	3052	3839	3419	3057	3536	3372	3339	4191	2791	3717	4019	2482	3422	3279	3952	3934	3566	3439	
3160	184	177	182	187	175	162	200	138	224	125	237	245	117	260	102	30	332	294	68	3439	
2838	179	181	183	170	192	188	174	132	230	228	134	96	266	246	116	359	3	345	17	3439	
4403	180	185	178	186	176	193	169	215	147	241	121	86	276	254	108	350	12	331	31	3439	
3170	203	173	166	167	163	201	194	236	126	226	136	89	273	253	109	15	347	7	355	3439	
3122	159	189	196	195	199	161	168	209	153	146	216	70	292	94	268	50	312	24	338	3439	
3778	191	198	165	205	158	160	190	214	148	156	206	244	118	264	98	37	325	19	343	3439	
3575	171	164	197	157	204	202	172	123	239	145	217	258	104	95	267	356	6	9	353	3439	
3455	234	152	213	135	208	150	155	130	141	235	238	272	90	100	262	11	351	344	18	3439	
3171	128	210	149	227	154	212	207	232	221	127	124	261	101	84	278	303	59	297	65	3439	
3724	143	140	218	133	223	240	231	142	137	151	233	259	103	242	120	328	34	33	329	3439	
3092	219	222	144	229	139	122	131	220	225	211	129	111	251	99	263	48	314	315	47	3439	
3806	73	71	277	75	279	243	280	250	92	115	257	283	269	77	74	64	298	22	340	3439	
3394	289	291	85	287	83	119	82	112	270	247	105	79	93	285	288	354	8	319	43	3439	
2732	69	72	274	255	113	265	271	248	80	106	252	78	275	76	281	357	5	330	32	3439	
3597	293	290	88	107	249	97	91	114	282	256	110	284	87	286	81	53	309	26	336	3439	
3477	2	21	324	348	339	326	320	317	56	52	61	46	311	60	337	352	54	55	58	3439	
3974	360	341	38	14	23	36	42	45	306	310	301	316	51	302	25	10	308	307	304	3439	
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	41	44	313	295	35	16	358	333	305	28	296	299	323	20	62	322	335	1	13	3439	
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4671	220	211	229	227	218	238	204	197	245	286	156	144	298	103	339	338	104	383	59	370	72	4641	
5415	210	233	217	226	219	201	241	208	234	178	264	180	262	131	311	331	111	378	64	63	379	4641	
4092	228	230	221	212	214	235	207	257	185	297	145	277	165	357	85	322	120	37	405	45	397	4641	
3740	223	216	225	209	232	181	261	194	248	293	149	280	162	126	316	108	334	422	20	382	60	4641	
5394	224	215	213	231	222	250	192	249	193	174	268	170	272	105	337	324	118	366	76	28	414	4641	
4050	258	206	188	260	256	200	237	189	195	158	284	301	141	364	78	344	98	26	416	435	7	4641	
5223	184	236	254	182	186	242	205	253	247	166	276	169	273	321	121	87	355	16	426	25	417	4641	
5289	252	246	203	187	183	244	240	191	243	155	287	172	270	345	97	90	352	395	47	380	62	4641	
4333	190	196	239	255	259	198	202	251	199	282	160	296	146	125	317	353	89	50	392	410	32	4641	
3916	289	303	163	271	274	157	266	288	147	142	148	150	275	124	318	319	123	40	402	2	440	4641	
4975	153	139	279	171	168	285	176	154	295	300	294	292	167	136	306	77	365	393	49	27	415	4641	
4732	304	179	302	305	267	152	161	159	164	291	143	269	177	329	113	84	358	372	70	376	66	4641	
4663	138	263	140	137	175	290	281	283	278	151	299	173	265	307	135	96	346	381	61	15	427	4641	
4344	348	79	107	336	325	320	116	308	115	88	313	328	314	333	95	100	132	54	388	367	75	4641	
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4539	361	362	356	91	130	133	110	359	315	101	93	119	343	102	360	92	330	35	407	419	23	4641	
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3944	437	428	68	71	10	53	421	430	44	31	67	13	33	399	390	58	436	386	368	433	65	4641	
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	73	441	404	42	406	69	413	55	424	420	34	385	431	439	418	39	17	4	46	30	51	4641	
©IJT	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641

23x23	mgc	5354	6127	6366	5639	6825	5083	7227	6043	5507	5521	6596	6985	4964	5972	5513	7320	6156	6555	6028	5455	6138	6716	6095
5730	268	261	266	271	259	246	284	222	308	209	321	329	201	344	186	114	416	378	152	73	457	482	48	6095
5954	263	265	267	254	276	272	258	216	314	312	218	180	350	330	200	443	87	429	101	54	476	69	461	6095
6213	264	269	262	270	260	277	253	299	231	325	205	170	360	338	192	434	96	415	115	503	27	528	2	6095
6781	287	257	250	251	247	285	278	320	210	310	220	173	357	337	193	99	431	91	439	481	49	43	487	6095
4859	243	273	280	279	283	245	252	293	237	230	300	154	376	178	352	134	396	108	422	525	5	21	509	6095
5552	275	282	249	289	242	244	274	298	232	240	290	328	202	348	182	121	409	103	427	28	502	516	14	6095
6941	255	248	281	241	288	286	256	207	323	229	301	342	188	179	351	440	90	93	437	523	7	47	483	6095
7596	318	236	297	219	292	234	239	214	225	319	322	356	174	184	346	95	435	428	102	42	488	65	465	6095
5366	212	294	233	311	238	296	291	316	305	211	208	345	185	168	362	387	143	381	149	521	9	41	489	6095
6011	227	224	302	217	307	324	315	226	221	235	317	343	187	326	204	412	118	117	413	52	478	480	50	6095
5919	303	306	228	313	223	206	215	304	309	295	213	195	335	183	347	132	398	399	131	522	8	520	10	6095
6220	157	155	361	159	363	327	364	334	176	199	341	367	353	161	158	148	382	106	424	76	454	23	507	6095
6382	373	375	169	371	167	203	166	196	354	331	189	163	177	369	372	438	92	403	127	36	494	58	472	6095
5650	153	156	358	339	197	349	355	332	164	190	336	162	359	160	365	441	89	414	116	499	31	462	68	6095
5599	377	374	172	191	333	181	175	198	366	340	194	368	171	370	165	137	393	110	420	501	29	62	468	6095
6661	86	105	408	432	423	410	404	401	140	136	145	130	395	144	421	436	138	139	142	45	485	514	16	6095
6099	444	425	122	98	107	120	126	129	390	394	385	400	135	386	109	94	392	391	388	500	30	80	450	6095
6228	405	402	133	151	411	430	88	113	141	418	150	147	123	426	384	124	111	445	433	37	493	506	24	6095
5374	125	128	397	379	119	100	442	417	389	112	380	383	407	104	146	406	419	85	97	17	513	518	12	6095
6336	517	519	75	512	34	510	459	38	479	495	486	470	63	78	79	475	46	53	72	497	56	67	15	6095
6647	13	11	455	18	496	20	71	492	51	35	44	60	467	452	451	55	484	477	458	33	474	463	515	6095
5972	446	498	61	508	453	448	3	70	490	26	511	64	505	471	39	1	4	74	57	464	449	6	447	6095
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9352	302	325	309	318	311	293	333	300	326	270	356	272	354	223	403	423	203	470	156	155	471	554	72	57	569	7825	
7722	320	322	313	304	306	327	299	349	277	389	237	369	257	449	177	414	212	129	497	137	489	561	65	56	570	7825	
6109	315	308	317	301	324	273	353	286	340	385	241	372	254	218	408	200	426	514	112	474	152	537	89	86	540	7825	
9038	316	307	305	323	314	342	284	341	285	266	360	262	364	197	429	416	210	458	168	120	506	13	613	1	625	7825	
7219	350	292	280	352	348	298	329	281	287	250	376	393	233	456	170	436	190	118	508	527	99	15	611	618	8	7825	
8693	276	334	346	274	278	328	297	345	339	258	368	261	365	413	213	179	447	108	518	117	509	544	82	595	31	7825	
8556	344	338	295	279	275	336	332	283	335	247	379	264	362	437	189	182	444	487	139	472	154	603	23	58	568	7825	
6874	282	288	331	347	351	290	294	343	291	374	252	388	238	217	409	445	181	142	484	502	124	24	602	16	610	7825	
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9107	396	271	394	397	359	244	253	251	256	383	235	361	269	421	205	176	450	464	162	468	158	594	32	593	33	7825	
7738	230	355	232	229	267	382	373	375	370	243	391	265	357	399	227	188	438	473	153	107	519	71	555	614	12	7825	
7666	440	171	199	428	417	412	208	400	207	180	405	420	406	425	187	192	224	146	480	459	167	73	553	26	600	7825	
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7232	453	454	448	183	222	225	202	451	407	193	185	211	435	194	452	184	422	127	499	511	115	541	85	572	54	7825	
7150	173	172	178	443	404	401	424	175	219	433	441	415	191	432	174	442	204	493	133	486	140	43	583	61	565	7825	
6669	97	106	466	463	524	481	113	104	490	503	467	521	501	135	144	476	98	148	166	101	469	589	37	20	606	7825	
9621	529	520	160	163	102	145	513	522	136	123	159	105	125	491	482	150	528	478	460	525	157	19	607	623	3	7825	
8204	461	93	130	492	128	465	121	479	110	114	500	149	103	95	116	495	517	530	488	504	483	543	83	59	567	7825	
6628	165	533	496	134	498	161	505	147	516	512	126	477	523	531	510	131	109	96	138	122	143	586	40	582	44	7825	
8222	35	580	621	91	10	624	88	69	599	70	63	578	74	592	534	617	590	38	66	49	84	47	559	574	573	7825	
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	546	545	564	42	558	575	79	41	28	549	21	76	597	562	615	14	7	566	25	576	17	18	548	75	581	7825	
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8605	364	369	362	370	360	377	353	399	331	425	305	270	460	438	292	534	196	515	215	603	127	628	102	75	655	644	86	9855	
9913	387	351	350	357	347	385	378	420	310	410	320	273	457	437	293	199	531	191	539	581	149	143	587	654	76	686	44	9855	
10287	343	379	380	373	383	345	352	393	337	330	400	254	476	278	452	234	496	208	522	625	105	121	609	53	677	66	664	9855	
9645	375	382	349	389	342	344	374	398	332	340	390	428	302	448	282	221	509	203	527	128	602	616	114	50	680	676	54	9855	
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10703	418	336	397	319	392	334	339	314	325	419	422	456	274	284	446	195	535	528	202	142	588	165	565	52	678	663	67	9855	
9785	312	394	333	411	338	396	391	416	405	311	308	445	285	268	462	487	243	481	249	621	109	141	589	57	673	43	687	9855	
8812	327	324	402	317	407	424	415	326	321	335	417	443	287	426	304	512	218	217	513	152	578	580	150	635	95	78	652	9855	
11566	403	406	328	413	323	306	315	404	409	395	313	295	435	283	447	232	498	499	231	622	108	620	110	669	61	19	711	9855	
8536	257	255	461	258	463	427	464	434	276	299	441	467	453	261	259	248	482	206	524	176	554	123	607	38	692	633	97	9855	
9353	473	475	269	472	267	303	266	296	454	431	289	263	277	469	471	538	192	503	227	136	594	158	572	91	639	699	31	9855	
10153	253	256	458	439	297	449	455	432	264	290	436	262	459	260	465	541	189	514	216	599	131	562	168	717	13	29	701	9855	
8580	477	474	272	291	433	281	275	298	466	440	294	468	271	470	265	237	493	210	520	601	129	162	568	719	11	640	90	9855	
11462	186	205	508	532	523	510	504	501	240	236	242	230	495	244	521	536	238	239	245	145	585	614	116	88	642	638	92	9855	
10042	544	525	222	198	207	220	226	229	490	494	488	500	235	486	209	194	492	491	485	600	130	180	550	696	34	1	729	9855	
9915	505	502	233	251	511	530	188	213	241	518	250	247	223	526	484	224	211	545	533	137	593	606	124	653	77	636	94	9855	
9537	225	228	497	479	219	200	542	517	489	212	480	483	507	204	246	506	519	185	197	117	613	618	112	46	684	47	683	9855	
8641	617	619	175	612	134	610	559	138	579	595	586	570	163	178	179	575	146	153	172	597	156	167	115	55	675	703	27	9855	
11491	113	111	555	118	596	120	171	592	151	135	144	160	567	552	551	155	584	577	558	133	574	563	615	99	631	65	665	9855	
10085	546	598	161	608	553	548	103	170	590	126	611	164	605	571	139	101	104	174	157	564	549	106	547	705	25	40	690	9855	
8859	184	132	569	122	177	182	627	560	140	604	119	566	125	159	591	629	626	556	573	166	181	624	183	720	10	17	713	9855	
8993	647	646	20	42	24	643	651	693	62	80	2	691	662	7	649	5	64	679	72	12	56	708	26	697	702	648	667	9855	
10440	83	84	710	688	706	87	79	37	668	650	728	39	68	723	81	725	666	51	658	718	674	22	704	33	28	82	63	9855	
10347	49	30	18	722	727	695	694	9	671	96	661	58	715	709	670	698	93	682	659	45	70	41	89	707	100	73	74	9855	
	681	700	712	8	3	35	36	721	59	634	69	672	15	21	60	32	637	48	71	685	660	689	641	23	630	657	656	9855	
©IJT	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855	9855

29x29	mgc	12023	12428	11777	12725	10638	15562	10056	13567	11266	13322	10201	13483	12672	11654	12691	13203	10207	13679	10552	12977	12971	10625	13112	11202	12942	10264	14108	11945	12209	
11450	420	411	429	427	418	438	404	397	445	486	356	344	498	303	539	538	304	583	259	570	272	138	704	730	112	95	747	841	1	12209	
13356	410	433	417	426	419	401	441	408	434	378	464	380	462	331	511	531	311	578	264	263	579	662	180	165	677	79	763	12	830	12209	
13525	428	430	421	412	414	435	407	457	385	497	345	477	365	557	285	522	320	237	605	245	597	669	173	164	678	28	814	81	761	12209	
10474	423	416	425	409	432	381	461	394	448	493	349	480	362	326	516	308	534	622	220	582	260	645	197	194	648	784	58	47	795	12209	
13217	424	415	413	431	422	450	392	449	393	374	468	370	472	305	537	524	318	566	276	228	614	121	721	109	733	89	753	40	802	12209	
11574	458	400	388	460	456	406	437	389	395	358	484	501	341	564	278	544	298	226	616	635	207	123	719	712	130	807	35	93	749	12209	
13606	384	442	454	382	386	436	405	453	447	366	476	369	473	521	321	287	555	216	626	225	617	652	190	703	139	788	54	98	744	12209	
11571	452	446	403	387	383	443	440	391	444	355	487	372	470	545	297	290	552	595	247	580	262	711	131	166	676	78	764	831	11	12209	
10394	390	396	439	455	459	399	402	451	398	482	360	496	346	325	517	553	289	250	592	610	232	132	710	124	718	7	835	101	741	12209	
12979	489	503	363	471	474	357	466	488	347	342	348	350	475	324	518	519	323	240	602	202	640	163	679	726	116	799	43	827	15	12209	
12046	353	339	479	371	368	485	376	354	495	500	494	492	367	336	506	277	565	593	249	227	615	647	195	728	114	73	769	48	794	12209	
12019	504	379	502	505	467	352	361	359	364	491	343	469	377	529	313	284	558	572	270	576	266	702	140	701	141	84	758	803	39	12209	
14527	338	463	340	337	375	490	481	483	478	351	499	373	465	507	335	296	546	581	261	215	627	179	663	722	120	102	740	107	735	12209	
9101	548	279	307	536	525	520	316	508	315	288	513	528	514	533	295	300	332	254	588	567	275	181	661	134	708	796	46	820	22	12209	
13545	294	563	535	306	317	322	526	334	527	554	329	314	328	309	547	542	510	208	634	219	623	147	695	198	644	105	737	768	74	12209	
11299	561	562	556	291	330	333	310	559	515	301	293	319	543	302	560	292	530	235	607	619	223	649	193	680	162	815	27	818	24	12209	
12499	281	280	286	551	512	509	532	283	327	541	549	523	299	540	282	550	312	601	241	594	248	151	691	169	673	779	63	55	787	12209	
11298	205	214	574	571	632	589	221	212	598	611	575	629	609	243	252	584	206	256	274	209	577	697	145	128	714	52	790	774	68	12209	
14086	637	628	268	271	210	253	621	630	244	231	267	213	233	599	590	258	636	586	568	633	265	127	715	731	111	829	13	828	14	12209	
13002	569	201	238	600	236	573	229	587	218	222	608	257	211	203	224	603	625	638	596	612	591	651	191	167	675	812	30	782	60	12209	
9981	273	641	604	242	606	269	613	255	624	620	234	585	631	639	618	239	217	204	246	230	251	694	148	690	152	20	822	51	791	12209	
12298	143	688	729	199	118	732	196	177	707	178	171	686	182	700	642	725	698	146	174	157	192	155	667	682	681	797	45	762	80	12209	
13169	699	154	113	643	724	110	646	665	135	664	671	156	660	142	200	117	144	696	668	685	650	687	175	160	161	809	33	806	36	12209	
12462	188	189	170	692	176	159	655	693	706	185	713	658	137	172	119	720	727	168	709	158	717	716	186	659	153	94	748	26	816	12209	
12078	654	653	672	150	666	683	187	149	136	657	129	184	705	670	723	122	115	674	133	684	125	126	656	183	689	804	38	106	736	12209	
11920	839	87	810	772	53	819	832	41	59	62	750	808	825	100	766	798	103	811	781	77	83	104	767	66	9	837	19	49	82	12209	
10392	3	755	32	70	789	23	10	801	783	780	92	34	17	742	76	44	739	31	61	765	759	738	75	776	833	5	823	793	760	12209	
13984	97	64	96	757	69	775	88	785	99	805	770	18	50	65	90	813	108	826	91	834	25	771	836	840	800	56	756	4	821	12209	
	745	778	746	85	773	67	754	57	743	37	72	824	792	777	752	29	734	16	751	8	817	71	6	2	42	786	86	838	21	12209	
©IJT	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209	12209

31x31	mgc	13867	14161	16008	14449	14597	14645	17660	12350	15702	16521	10818	15917	15294	17029	11810	15253	17176	14455	15090	13260	13651	17748	14955	13328	16790	13570	14854	15462	15244	15666	14911	
12902	484	477	482	487	475	462	500	438	524	425	537	545	417	560	402	330	632	594	368	289	673	698	264	840	122	842	120	60	902	854	108	14911	
17282	479	481	483	470	492	488	474	432	530	528	434	396	566	546	416	659	303	645	317	270	692	285	677	830	132	748	214	905	57	99	863	14911	
12804	480	485	478	486	476	493	469	515	447	541	421	386	576	554	408	650	312	631	331	719	243	744	218	191	771	760	202	858	104	924	38	14911	
14129	503	467	466	473	463	501	494	536	426	526	436	389	573	553	409	315	647	307	655	697	265	259	703	770	192	802	160	849	113	879	83	14911	
15772	459	495	496	489	499	461	468	509	453	446	516	370	592	394	568	350	612	324	638	741	221	237	725	169	793	117	845	49	913	20	942	14911	
14696	491	498	465	505	458	460	490	514	448	456	506	544	418	564	398	337	625	319	643	244	718	732	230	166	796	792	170	106	856	7	955	14911	
16390	471	464	497	457	504	502	472	423	539	445	517	558	404	395	567	656	306	309	653	739	223	263	699	201	761	130	832	914	48	45	917	14911	
15790	534	452	513	435	508	450	455	430	441	535	538	572	390	400	562	311	651	644	318	258	704	281	681	168	794	779	183	53	909	58	904	14911	
14296	428	510	449	527	454	512	507	532	521	427	424	561	401	384	578	603	359	597	365	737	225	257	705	173	789	159	803	952	10	947	15	14911	
15285	443	440	518	433	523	540	531	442	437	451	533	559	403	542	420	628	334	333	629	268	694	696	266	751	211	194	768	872	90	13	949	14911	
16090	519	522	444	529	439	422	431	520	525	511	429	411	551	399	563	348	614	615	347	738	224	736	226	785	177	135	827	921	41	6	956	14911	
13369	373	371	577	374	579	543	580	550	392	415	557	583	569	377	375	364	598	322	640	292	670	239	723	154	808	749	213	933	29	893	69	14911	
14140	589	591	385	588	383	419	382	412	570	547	405	379	393	585	587	654	308	619	343	252	710	274	688	207	755	815	147	76	886	910	52	14911	
13074	369	372	574	555	413	565	571	548	380	406	552	378	575	376	581	657	305	630	332	715	247	678	284	833	129	145	817	954	8	855	107	14911	
17299	593	590	388	407	549	397	391	414	582	556	410	584	387	586	381	353	609	326	636	717	245	278	684	835	127	756	206	95	867	846	116	14911	
13883	302	321	624	648	639	626	620	617	356	352	358	346	611	360	637	652	355	354	361	261	701	730	232	204	758	754	208	91	871	877	85	14911	
16910	660	641	338	314	323	336	342	345	606	610	604	616	351	602	325	310	607	608	601	716	246	296	666	812	150	182	780	876	86	3	959	14911	
16997	621	618	349	367	627	646	304	329	357	634	366	363	339	642	600	340	327	661	649	253	709	722	240	769	193	752	210	935	27	80	882	14911	
11731	341	344	613	595	335	316	658	633	605	328	596	599	623	320	362	622	635	301	313	233	729	734	228	162	800	163	799	930	32	898	64	14911	
15175	733	735	291	728	250	726	675	254	695	711	702	686	279	294	295	691	262	269	288	713	272	283	231	171	791	819	143	51	911	946	16	14911	
14898	229	227	671	234	712	236	287	708	267	251	260	276	683	668	667	271	700	693	674	249	690	679	731	215	747	181	781	100	862	888	74	14911	
16765	662	714	277	724	669	664	219	286	706	242	727	280	721	687	255	217	220	290	273	680	665	222	663	821	141	156	806	110	852	35	927	14911	
14111	300	248	685	238	293	298	743	676	256	720	235	682	241	275	707	745	742	672	689	282	297	740	299	836	126	133	829	89	873	23	939	14911	
12347	763	762	136	158	140	759	767	809	178	196	118	807	778	123	765	121	180	795	188	128	172	824	142	813	818	764	783	94	868	940	22	14911	
17461	199	200	826	804	822	203	195	153	784	766	844	155	184	839	197	841	782	167	774	834	790	138	820	149	144	198	179	105	857	21	941	14911	
15124	165	146	134	838	843	810	811	125	787	212	777	174	831	825	786	814	209	798	775	161	186	157	205	823	216	189	190	56	906	5	957	14911	
14522	797	816	828	124	119	152	151	837	175	750	185	788	131	137	176	148	753	164	187	801	776	805	757	139	746	773	772	953	9	915	47	14911	
14913	847	848	11	59	861	944	880	937	883	864	887	62	891	43	14	36	30	878	103	44	907	42	50	54	46	889	66	4	866	929	936	14911	
14477	115	114	951	903	101	18	82	25	79	98	75	900	71	919	948	926	932	84	859	918	55	920	912	908	916	73	896	958	96	33	26	14911	
14698	865	960	938	112	853	892	39	81	899	895	950	884	88	93	102	77	61	945	943	87	925	894	40	72	961	31	111	92	28	928	65	14911	
	97	2	24	850	109	70	923	881	63	67	12	78	874	869	860	885	901	17	19	875	37	68	922	890	1	931	851	870	934	34	897	14911	
©IJT	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911	14911

Remark 1. In this case, the magic squares of orders 7, 11, 15, 19, ... are with magic squares of order 3 in the first corner or we can replace by magic rectangle of order 3 × 5. The magic squares of orders 9, 13, 17, 21, are with magic squares of order 5 in the first corner or we can replace by magic rectangle of order 5 × 7.

Above we have given magic squares of orders 6 to 31. Total work is up to order 50. The complete list as excel file is give at the above mentioned link of author’s web-site.

A similar kind of work for the **double-digits bordered striped magic squares** of two types, i.e., **opposite and cycle**, refer to author's work [82].

Acknowledgement

This work on **striped** and **semi-striped** magic squares is done manually, but for the **general double digits bordered** [81] and **cornered magic squares** [86], the readers can study using software by H. White [1]. The author is thankful to H. White for providing scripts for previous works.

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>

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